

Necrophages and necrophiles: a review of their antibacterial defenses and biotechnological potential

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ABSTRACT

With antibiotic resistance on the rise, there is an urgent need for new antibacterial drugs and products to treat or prevent infection. Many such products in current use, for example human and veterinary antibiotics and antimicrobial food preservatives, were discovered and developed from nature. Natural selection acts on all living organisms and the presence of bacterial competitors or pathogens in an environment can favor the evolution of antibacterial adaptations. In this review, we ask if vultures, blow flies and other carrion users might be a good starting point for antibacterial discovery based on the selection pressure they are under from bacterial disease. Dietary details are catalogued for over 600 of these species, bacterial pathogens associated with the diets are described, and an overview of the antibacterial defenses contributing to disease protection is given. Biotechnological applications for these defenses are then discussed, together with challenges facing developers and possible solutions. Examples include use of (a) the antimicrobial peptide (AMP) gene *sarcotoxin IA* to improve crop resistance to bacterial disease, (b) peptide antibiotics such as serrawettin W2 as antibacterial drug leads, (c) lectins for targeted drug delivery, (d) bioconversion-generated chitin as an antibacterial biomaterial, (e) bacteriocins as antibacterial food preservatives and (f) mutualistic microbiota bacteria as alternatives to antibiotics in animal feed. We show that carrion users encounter a diverse range of bacterial pathogens through their diets and interactions, have evolved many antibacterial defenses, and are a promising source of genes, molecules and microbes for medical, agricultural and food industry product development.

Keywords: scavenger; necrophagous; necrophilous; immunity; symbiosis; biotechnology; drug discovery; biocides; biomaterials; probiotics

Introduction

Antibiotic resistance is a serious global problem, contributing to an estimated 5 million deaths per year [1] and eroding our ability to perform medical interventions such as surgery and cancer chemotherapy safely [2]. To meet this challenge, efforts are being made to discover new antibacterial and antivirulence drugs capable of replacing those antibiotics that are no longer working [3]. Attempts are also being made to identify new antibiotic potentiators, drugs that suppress bacterial resistance and restore or enhance antibiotic activity [4]. Work is underway to reduce antibiotic consumption too as this is a major driver of resistance and a means to decelerate the emergence of new resistant strains of bacteria. In human health and healthcare, this may be achievable through the development of new or improved vaccines [5], colonization-resistant medical implants [6], food sanitizers [7] and other antibacterial products [8]. In agriculture, innovative methods of infection prevention are likewise being explored, including the use of probiotics in livestock and poultry production [9,10] and the development of disease-resistant crops [11].

Bioprospecting has been an important source of many pharmaceutical and agricultural products including medically useful antibiotics such as streptomycin and chlortetracycline [12], the antibiotic potentiator clavulanic acid [13], and the veterinary antibiotics novobiocin and avilamycin [14]. The antibacterial food preservatives nisin and sorbate [15] and versatile cephalosporin-class antibiotics [16] were also discovered and developed from nature. Antibacterial bioprospecting can be performed by randomly screening organisms for activity, but a more rational approach is to select niches or species based on ecological, historical or other information [12]. For example, Waksman and Schatz screened soil bacteria based on observations of microbial antagonism within soil and discovered streptomycin [17]. Also, Brotzu screened local marine fungi after observing that *Salmonella*-contaminated sewage was not infecting swimmers and discovered the cephalosporin C-producer *Acremonium chrysogenum* [18]. In addition, Lederle Laboratories screened soil streptomycetes based on Waksman and Schatz's prior success with these bacteria and discovered chlortetracycline [19].

Most antibacterial bioprospecting studies to date have focused on microbes and plants, but animals such as the Eurasian griffon vulture (*Gyps fulvus*) [20], Atlantic hagfish (*Myxine glutinosa*) [21] and common green bottle fly (*Lucilia sericata*) [22] are also attracting interest. These animals feed on decomposing animal carcasses populated with large numbers of bacteria, and selection pressure from pathogens in this diet could have favored the evolution of enhanced host defenses [20-22]. In this review, we catalogue some of the different animal species feeding on animal carcasses, and species in a closely related group immediately above them in the food chain. We present information on the bacteria and toxins these animals are exposed to, and the traits proposed to protect them. Because vertebrate pathogens are sometimes nonpathogenic in invertebrates (e.g. *Clostridium botulinum* [23]) and *vice versa* (e.g. *Bacillus thuringiensis* [24]), this information is presented separately. Vertebrate and invertebrate defenses are also described separately, since vertebrates have a more complex immune system. Applications for these defenses are then discussed from a medical, agricultural and food perspective, and the review concludes with suggestions for future research.

Necrophagy and necrophily: definitions and related terms

‘Necrophagy’ is defined as the act of eating ‘carrion’, the decaying flesh or tissue of dead animals. The term ‘scavenging’ is used to describe this feeding behavior too, but is less precise, encompassing also the consumption of dead plant material [25]. Necrophagous animals differ in their level of dependence on and adaptation to carrion feeding. Animals are categorized as ‘obligate necrophages’ if they use carrion as their sole or main food source and rely on carrion for survival or reproduction (Fig. 1a). Animals consuming carrion opportunistically and retaining the traits needed to kill prey or use other food sources are considered ‘facultative necrophages’ (Fig. 1b) [26]. Lastly, not all of the animals visiting carrion are necrophagous. Some are seeking live carrion inhabitants (e.g. insect larvae or pupae) to eat or to parasitize. These animals are categorized as ‘necrophilous’ (Fig. 1c) and sub-categorized as ‘predators’ and ‘parasitoids’ respectively [27].

Necrophagy and necrophily among vertebrates

Examples of vertebrate necrophages and necrophiles

Among terrestrial vertebrates, vultures are the only obligate necrophages (Suppl Table 1). Vultures are highly specialized, their large size enabling them to consume large, infrequent meals, their gliding flight helping them conserve energy, and an excellent olfactory sense helping them locate carrion [29]. Among marine vertebrates, some Myxinidae (hagfish) species rely heavily on carrion and may also be obligate necrophages. Like vultures, hagfish can survive extended periods without eating, are highly mobile, and can detect carrion from long distances [30].

Although few vertebrate species are obligate necrophages, there are an enormous number of facultative necrophages. Almost all carnivorous vertebrates use carrion as a food source [e.g. *Aquila rapax* (tawny eagles)], as do some omnivores [e.g. *Vulpes vulpes* (red foxes)] and even some largely herbivorous animals [e.g. *Neotoma floridana* (Eastern woodrats)] (Suppl Table 1). Quantities of carrion consumed vary greatly amongst facultative necrophages. For example, *Sus scrofa* (wild boars) consume carrion as ~15% of their diet [31], *Coryphaenoides armatus* (abyssal grenadiers) as ~69% of their diet [32], and *Hyaena brunnea* (brown hyenas) as up to 90% of their diet [29].

Necrophily is less commonly reported for vertebrates than invertebrates but does occur. For example, *Cyanopica cyanus* (azure-winged magpies), *Pica pica* (Eurasian magpies) and red fox puppies feed on insects at the carcass, and abyssal grenadiers feed on amphipods (Suppl Table 1).

Bacteria and toxins encountered by vertebrate necrophages and necrophiles

Whilst a necrophagous diet has certain advantages (e.g. high protein and energy content; does not need to be chased or subdued like live prey), there are also important risks including exposure to bacterial pathogens and toxins. One source of these pathogens and toxins is the carcass itself if the animal has died of infection (Suppl Table 2). Wildlife can die from many bacterial diseases (e.g. *Bacillus anthracis*

toxico-infection of ungulates; *Francisella tularensis* infection of rabbits and rodents; *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Pasteurella multocida* infections of deer; *Yersinia pestis* infection of rodents). Bacterial diseases also kill livestock (e.g. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* infection of cattle, sheep and pigs) and other animals (e.g. *F. tularensis* and *Y. pestis* infections of cats). Post-mortem microbiological culture shows bacteria can remain viable in these carcasses (Suppl Table 2).

A second source of bacteria and toxins is other necrophagous and necrophilous animals visiting the carcass. These animals can harbor many pathogens (e.g. muscid flies carry *Aeromonas hydrophila*, *B. anthracis*, *Campylobacter coli*, *Campylobacter jejuni* and *Salmonella enterica* [33-35]; blow flies, flesh flies and dermestid beetles carry *Clostridium botulinum* [23,36]; carrion crows, rooks and red foxes carry *Mycobacterium avium* subsp. *paratuberculosis* [37]; wild boar carry *Mycobacterium bovis* [38]; carrion crows and rooks carry *P. multocida* [39]). Considerable inter- and intra-species contact is possible between these necrophages and necrophiles, especially if a carcass is large, there is a mass mortality event, or the animals feed communally (Suppl Table 3). Any such contact will provide opportunities for disease transmission [29].

Additional sources of pathogens and toxins necrophages are exposed to are the dead animal's microbiota and environmental species growing in or on the carcass (e.g. *C. botulinum* [40], *Clostridium novyi* [41], *Clostridium perfringens* [42], *Mycoplasma hyorhinis* [43], *Proteus mirabilis*, *Proteus vulgaris* [44,45], *S. enterica*, *Streptococcus suis* [43]). Lastly, many of the risks described above for necrophages also apply to necrophiles. This includes direct risks from their diet because the live carrion inhabitants that necrophiles prey upon (e.g. fly larvae) can accumulate bacterial pathogens and toxins from the carcass (e.g. *B. anthracis* [37], *C. botulinum* [36] and botulinum toxin [23]).

Traits reducing risk of disease in vertebrate necrophages and necrophiles

Traits proposed to protect vertebrate carrion users from bacteria can be divided into four categories: (a) anatomies less sensitive to bacterial toxins, (b) risk reduction behaviors, (c) innate immunity and (d) adaptive immunity. Innate immune defenses currently hold most promise from an antibacterial biotechnology perspective, but information will be presented on all four categories as it could be useful in prioritizing or deprioritizing animals for further study.

Most anatomical adaptations protecting animals from disease serve a barrier function (i.e. they stop bacteria and toxins entering the body or stop them reaching sterile body sites) and will be discussed below as part of the innate immune system. In vultures however, there is evidence of anatomical adaptation beyond their outer body surface and mucous membranes. A study comparing vultures and roosters shows the former are $1-2 \times 10^4$ times as resistant to intracardially administered botulinum toxin, with subsequent work on isolated biventer cervicis neuromuscular preparations suggesting vultures' presynaptic nerve endings are less toxin-sensitive [46].

Numerous risk reduction behaviors have been documented too. These include reaching carcasses quickly (e.g. Atlantic hagfish find carrion within minutes or hours [47]), avoiding older carcasses (e.g. turkey vultures eat 1-day-old carrion in preference to 4-day-old carrion [48]), avoiding carrion consumption in summer when decomposition is more rapid (e.g. gray wolves [49]), preferring predator-killed animals (e.g. common ravens [50]), feeding on bones rather than meat (e.g. bearded vultures [51]), avoiding carnivore carcasses (e.g. stone martens [52]), and sunning their plumage after feeding (e.g. black vultures [53]). Not all carrion users practice these precautions (Suppl Table 3).

The innate immune system comprises, as its first line of defense, different types of barrier. Examples of dermatological barriers include bald heads in vultures and slime production in hagfish. Bald heads, in addition to facilitating thermoregulation [54], decrease the accumulation of putrefying material during feeding [55]. Also, analysis of Atlantic hagfish slime shows it has elevated lysozyme activity compared to other epidermal fish secretions [56]. Moving onto gastrointestinal barriers, some

necrophages hold food in their stomachs for an extended period (e.g. ~4-12 hours for wolves and dogs versus ~0.5-2 hours in primates) [57]. Inter-study comparisons of animal stomach acidity are challenging because of the many variables affecting measurements [58], but very low pH values have been documented in necrophages such as the white-backed vulture (pH 1.2) [59]. Strong stomach acidity in vultures may be due to adaptations in *ATP4B* and other genes of the gastric acid secretion pathway [60]. Some necrophages also have shorter intestinal tracts, so subsequent transit and excretion of the food bolus and any surviving bacteria is more rapid (e.g. 5-8 hours in dogs versus ≥ 12 -60 hours in primates) [57]. Barriers present at both dermatological and gastrointestinal locations include mucus, antimicrobial peptides (AMPs), antimicrobial proteins and microbiota organisms. Positive selection and rapid evolution have been detected in mucin synthesis and mucus secretion genes in vultures and hyenas [60], novel AMPs and antimicrobial proteins (e.g. myxinidin, CRISP protein) have been identified in the Atlantic hagfish and Patagonia green racer snake [61,62], and antibiotic- and bacteriocin-producing microbiota bacteria have been detected in several vulture species [20,63].

In addition to barriers, innate immunity has numerous regulatory, humoral and cellular components, and there is evidence of adaptation in these too. In vultures, convergent changes have been detected in the genes encoding *STING*, a protein that controls type I interferon and proinflammatory cytokine transcription [60]. Humoral modifications include positive selection of the gene for opsonin alpha2-HS glycoprotein in vultures [64], and cellular changes include novel toll like receptor genes in vultures [64] and novel lysosomal AMPs in Komodo dragons [65].

Some carrion users have modifications in their adaptive immune systems too. In vultures, changes have been detected in genes important for B-cell development (*PIK3API*) [64], Tfh-cell and B-cell differentiation (*BCL6*) [66], IgA and IgM production (*JCHAIN*), and IgA and IgM transport to the GI tract surface (*PIGR*) [60]. Also, whilst *C. botulinum* toxins typically kill animals at concentrations lower than those needed to generate humoral immunity, anti-botulinum antibodies have been detected in turkey vultures, American crows and coyotes [67]. Comparatively little information is available on cell-based

adaptive immunity in necrophages, but positive selection and rapid evolution have been detected in vulture genes affecting T-cell homeostasis [60].

Necrophagy and necrophily among invertebrates

Examples of invertebrate necrophages and necrophiles

Necrophagous invertebrates outnumber necrophagous vertebrates considerably, with species numbers in some locations reaching over 500 [68]. Many adult invertebrates use carrion not just as a food source for themselves but also their offspring, laying eggs or larvae in the carcass (e.g. blow flies, flesh flies) or its vicinity (e.g. silphine beetles, microphorine beetles) [69].

Obligately necrophagous terrestrial invertebrates include the piophilid flies *Centrophlebomyia furcata* and *Thyreophora cynophila*, microphorine beetles such as *Nicrophorus concolor*, and the vulture bees *Trigona crassipes* and *T. necrophaga* (Suppl Table 4). These species have specialist traits enabling them to quickly locate carrion (e.g. *Nicrophorus* spp. have sensitive antennal chemosensors [70]), chase away competitors (e.g. *T. necrophaga* [71]), or reduce the need for competition by niche partitioning (e.g. *Nicrophorus* spp. [72]). Marine invertebrates proposed to be obligately necrophagous include the malacostracans *Anonyx sarsi*, *Charcotia obesa*, *Paralicella caperesca* and *Tryphosa nana* (Suppl Table 4). Specialist traits consistent with obligate necrophagy include the ability to rapidly find carrion (e.g. *T. nana* [73]), gorge themselves (e.g. *P. caperesca* has expandable intestines [74]) and survive on infrequent meals (e.g. *C. obesa* can survive 18 months without meals [75]).

Many hundreds of invertebrates are facultatively necrophagous, some examples listed in Suppl Table 4. The most dominant orders terrestrially are flies (especially blow flies and flesh flies) and beetles (especially dermestid, hister, rove and silphine beetles). Traits enabling these organisms to outcompete other species include a keen sense of smell (e.g. flesh flies [76]), high fecundity (e.g. blow flies [77]) and the ability to repel competitors (e.g. *Necrodes surinamensis* [78]). Information on the relative dominance

of facultatively necrophagous marine invertebrates is limited, but species detected in large numbers regionally include the malacostracans *Cirolana harfordi*, *Coenobita perlatus*, *Hirondellea gigas* and *Tmetonyx cicada*, the nematode *Pontonema vulgare*, and the nemertean *Parborlasia corrugatus* [79].

Invertebrate necrophiles may be predaceous or parasitic (Suppl Table 4). Predators feed on live carrion inhabitants (e.g. *Carcinops pumilio* eats fly eggs [69]) and parasitoids use carrion inhabitants as hosts (e.g. *Nasonia vitripennis* lays its eggs in blow fly pupae [80]).

Bacteria and toxins encountered by invertebrate necrophages and necrophiles

Invertebrate necrophages and necrophiles are exposed to many pathogens during feeding and reproduction. These include bacteria in the carcass (e.g. *Bacillus cereus* in wildlife and livestock [43,81]; *Bacillus circulans*, *Bacillus thuringiensis*, *Brevibacillus laterosporus* and *Lysinibacillus sphaericus* in cattle [82]; *B. thuringiensis* in insects [24,83]; *Clostridioides difficile* and *Paraclostridium bifermentans* in human remains [41]; *Clostridium perfringens* in wildlife, humans and livestock [42,43,81]; *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Pseudomonas chlororaphis* in livestock [44,81]; *S. enterica* in wildlife and livestock [43,81]; *Serratia marcescens* in boars and mice [43,45]; *Staphylococcus aureus* in livestock [84]; *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* in marine life [85]). Other carrion visitors can also be a source of bacterial pathogens (e.g. *B. cereus*, *L. sphaericus* and *Paenibacillus alvei* from *Musca domestica* [34]; *S. enterica* from *Carcinops pumilio*, *Hydrotaea aenescens* and *M. domestica* [34,86,87]; *S. aureus* and *Staphylococcus sciuri* from *M. domestica* [34]). These bacteria cause disease in invertebrates through direct colonization (e.g. *L. monocytogenes*) and toxin production (e.g. *B. thuringiensis* and *L. sphaericus*) [83,88].

Traits reducing risk of disease in invertebrate necrophages and necrophiles

Traits proposed to protect invertebrate carrion users from bacteria can be divided into four categories: (a) risk reduction behaviors, (b) innate immunity, (c) social immunity and (d) detoxification systems. Risk

reduction behaviors observed include reaching carcasses quickly (e.g. blow flies and flesh flies find dead animals within minutes [76]), avoiding older carcasses (e.g. *Menippe mercenaria* eats fresh carrion 2.5 times more frequently than microbe-laden carrion [89]), feeding on carrion mainly in winter (e.g. *T. cynophila* [90]), and grooming their external surfaces (e.g. *Phormia regina* [91]).

Moving onto innate immunity, an important explanation for the general resistance of arthropods to bacterial disease is their exoskeletal cuticle. This barrier is constructed from the antibacterial polymer chitin, it is physically difficult for bacteria to penetrate [92], and is further reinforced in some necrophages (e.g. *Solenopsis invicta*) by the application of antibacterial secretions [93]. The digestive tract of many insects, including necrophagous *Calliphora* and *Dermestes* spp., is also partly protected by the cuticle [94,95] and a second chitin barrier called a peritrophic membrane or matrix [96,97]. Other digestive tract barriers include acidic conditions [e.g. *Camponotus floridanus* (pH 2) [98]], AMPs and lysozymes (e.g. *M. domestica* [99,100]), and mutualistic microbiota bacteria (e.g. antibiotic-producing *Myroides odoratimimus* in *Sarcophaga* sp. [101]). *Hermetia illucens* and *M. domestica* encode especially large numbers of lysozymes, 36 and 34, respectively (versus ~10 in other fly species) [102].

For bacteria that breach the above barriers and reach the hemocoel (circulatory system), there are additional innate defenses. Lining the hemocoel is a multi-functional tissue known as the fat body [103] that secretes molecules important for humoral immunity (e.g. AMPs [104,105], lysozymes and other antibacterial proteins [106]). Circulating fatty acids may provide protection too [107]. Also present in the hemocoel are immune cells called hemocytes. Some hemocytes (e.g. crystal cells, oenocytoids) contribute to humoral immunity by triggering phenoloxidase activation and melanization, a process where bacteria are bombarded with reactive oxygen species and sealed within melanin [108,109]. Other hemocytes (e.g. granulocytes, plasmatocytes) are phagocytic [109,110]. Pattern recognition receptors (PRPs) are responsible for detecting bacterial pathogens and activating the above effectors and, in some necrophages, expansion in the genes encoding these receptors has been detected (e.g. Nimrod PRPs in *M. domestica* [111]).

Social immunity resembles the above defenses in that it encompasses both behavioral and physiological traits but differs in that the individual expressing the trait is not the sole or main beneficiary. Several such traits become apparent during reproduction and brood care, with some mating necrophages avoiding old carrion (e.g. *N. vespilloides* [112]), rolling away or burying carrion (e.g. *Canthon cyanellus*, *Nicrophorus* spp. [113]), eviscerating carcasses (e.g. *N. vespilloides* [114]), desiccating carcasses (e.g. *S. invicta* [115]), smearing carcasses with antibacterial and toxin-degrading exudates (e.g. *N. vespilloides* [106,116]), and feeding antibacterial exudates to larvae (e.g. solenopsins in *S. invicta* [117]). The secretion of antibacterial factors onto carrion by larval broods (e.g. *Calliphora vicina* and *N. vespilloides*) is also a form of social immunity [118,119].

In addition to the above behavioral and immunological defenses, genome sequencing has detected expansions in the genes encoding detoxification enzymes in some necrophages (e.g. cytochrome P450 enzymes in *H. illucens* [102] and *M. domestica* [111]). These enzymes may help protect necrophages from bacterial toxins encountered in their diet.

Biotechnological potential of necrophage and necrophile defenses

Antimicrobial peptides (≤50 amino acids or ≤5.5 kDa)

Carrion users are a rich source of AMPs including cathelicidins, cecropins, defensins, dipterocins, histone-derived AMPs, knottin-like peptides, proline-rich peptides and sarconesins (Suppl Table 5). Whole-genome and transcriptome sequencing of *H. illucens*, the black soldier fly, has shown it encodes 44-47 AMPs (excl. attacins), one of the largest AMP repertoires identified in any insect to date [102,120]. AMPs called bacteriocins are also produced by the microbiotas of some necrophages [20]. Several studies have purified the above AMPs and determined their minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs; Table 1a). Also, some studies have identified AMPs that are not just inhibitory but bactericidal (e.g. *H. illucens* DLP2 [121], myxinidin [61]) and active, not just against planktonic bacteria, but bacterial biofilms (e.g.

C. vicina AMPs [104]). Very little toxicity data is available for these AMPs, but the half maximal cytotoxic concentration (CC_{50}) determined for DLP2 against mouse macrophages is $>128 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ [121] (giving a preliminary selectivity index value of >32). Sarconesin shows good selectivity in *in vitro* studies too [122].

Applications proposed for the above peptides include antibacterial [22,123] and anti-biofilm drugs [104]. Minimum requirements for this development pathway are under constant review, but MIC values must typically be $<10 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and selectivity index values >10 if the end goal is a drug that can be used systemically [12]. Improvements in antibacterial potency are sometimes possible through medicinal chemistry optimization, as demonstrated with the Atlantic hagfish- and Komodo dragon-inspired synthetic peptides HF-18 [21] and DRGN-1 [124]. In addition to direct-acting antibacterial and anti-biofilm drugs, the development of AMPs as antibiotic potentiators is an option. Many AMPs reduce the structural integrity of the bacterial cell envelope, enabling intracellular-acting antibiotics to reach their targets more easily [125]. For AMPs unsuited to systemic use, possible applications include topical medications to treat skin infections [126] or, for AMPs with dual antibacterial and immunostimulatory activity, gels [124] or hydrogels [127] for dressing wounds. AMPs active against foodborne pathogens could be useful as food preservatives [20].

Factors hampering AMP development for the above applications are their instability to proteases, low bioavailability, hemolytic activity [125] and cost of synthesis [126], but these may be resolvable. For example, the stability of linear AMPs can be improved by structural modifications (e.g. stapling) [128,129]. Also, for localized infections, novel delivery systems such as inhalable microparticles can be used to bypass the GI tract and bloodstream [130]. Options for systemic administration are being developed too [131]. Cost of AMP synthesis may be reducible by using short derivatives of the parent peptide [126] or developing more efficient heterologous expression systems [132]. Lastly, many of the above problems could be resolved by using AMPs as templates for the rational design of peptidomimetic drugs or compounds [131].

Small-molecule antibacterials (<900 Da)

Small-molecule antibacterials produced by necrophages, necrophiles and their microbiotas include alkaloids (e.g. solenopsins A to C [142]), 1-lysophosphatidylethanolamine [146], peptide antibiotics (e.g. nicrophorusamide A [145], serrawettin W2 [144]), phenolic acids (e.g. *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid, *p*-hydroxyphenylacetic acid [147]) and proline diketopiperazine [147]. MIC data, where available, is presented in Table 1b. One possible application for such compounds is antibacterial drug leads [144,145]. Because they are small in size and contain few amino acids, bioavailability and proteolytic stability are less likely to be problematic with these compounds than AMPs. Another option for these molecules is their development as antibacterial biocides for use in medicine, dentistry or the food industry [148]. Some *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid derivatives already have a long history of use as preservatives [149], and the solenopsins (from *S. invicta*) display a useful combination of bactericidal [143] and anti-biofilm activity [148].

Lysozymes and other antibacterial proteins (>50 amino acids or >5.5 kDa)

Four types of lysozyme are recognized within the animal kingdom, c- (chicken), g- (goose), i- (invertebrate) and ch- (chalaropsis) types, with multiple variations of each sometimes present in a single species (e.g. nine c-type and four i-type lysozymes in *N. vespilloides* [106]). These proteins bind and hydrolyze exposed peptidoglycan, and are therefore active against Gram-positive bacteria [150]. Some c-, g- and i-type lysozymes also have a second, non-enzymatic mechanism of action, attributed to cationic, hydrophilic and lipophilic domains, which broadens their spectrum of activity to include Gram-negative bacteria [151]. Other antibacterial proteins detected in carrion users include attacins, cathepsin D-like proteins, coleopterins, crustins, cysteine-rich secretory proteins (CRISPs) and hexamerins (Suppl Table 6). Very little quantitative data is available on the activity and toxicity of these proteins, but patagonin-CRISP (from the Patagonia green racer) has an MIC of 7.5 to 15 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ against Gram-negative bacteria and a CC_{50} of $>120 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ against Vero cells [62] (giving a selectivity index value of >8).

Lysozymes are already used in industry as food preservatives [151] and for recovery of intracellular products in biopharmaceutical production [152]. New applications proposed for these antibacterial proteins and others include antibacterial therapies [62,153], antibiotic delivery systems [154], biomaterial constituents [154,155] and alternatives to antibiotics in livestock feed [156]. Lysozymes could be useful as antibacterial therapies or biomaterial constituents because, in addition to killing growing bacteria, they are active against dormant, multidrug-resistant and biofilm bacteria, and have a low propensity to generate resistance [153,154]. Lysozymes could also be useful in antibiotic delivery systems because they stabilize antibiotic-loaded liposomes, bind to bacteria, and increase the activity of the antibiotic being delivered [154]. Lysozymes hold promise as livestock feed additives too, since they increase feed efficiency and growth, and reduce intestinal counts of bacterial pathogens [156].

Obstacles limiting development of the above proteins for new applications are their inactivation by low pH, proteolytic enzymes and organic solvents [157,158]. Also, because proteins are larger in size and have more complex structures than AMPs, they are more likely to generate hypersensitivity reactions [159] and are more challenging and costly to manufacture [130,159]. Not all proteins have these limitations though [154] and, for those that do, there may be workarounds. For example, stability problems could be overcome by structural modifications [158], and the risk of hypersensitivity could be reduced by using short antibacterial peptides derived from the parent lysozyme [154,159] or protein [135]. Production difficulties could be overcome by using shorter peptides too [135,154,159] or by developing more cost-efficient heterologous expression systems [130].

Lectins

In addition to the proteins above, a small number of lectins have been identified in carrion users (e.g. *Chrysomya megacephala* [160], *Dermestes frischii* [161], *M. domestica* [162], *Sarcophaga bullata* [163]). Lectins are carbohydrate-binding proteins and glycoproteins that serve as pattern recognition receptors within the innate immune system [164]. Lectins bind selectively to different carbohydrate-containing

molecules on bacteria (e.g. lipopolysaccharide, lipoteichoic acid) and immune system cells, triggering AMP upregulation, phagocytosis and other responses [165,166]. In binding to bacterial cells, lectins may also exert direct effects of their own, including cell wall growth inhibition and damage [164,165].

Possible applications for lectins include drugs, drug delivery systems and vaccine adjuvants. Lectins are being investigated as antibacterial drugs because their interaction with bacterial cell wall carbohydrates can damage bacteria and block bacterial attachment to host tissue (Fig. 2a) [165]. Lectins are also being investigated for use in drug delivery as their high affinity for bacterial surface molecules could facilitate the targeting of treatments to infected tissue (Fig. 2b) [164]. Lastly, lectins could be developed as immunomodulatory drugs or vaccine adjuvants since they enhance macrophage activity, cytokine secretion [167] and B-cell production [168].

Lectins share many of the same limitations as antibacterial peptides and proteins, including inactivation by low pH and proteolytic enzymes, and poor bioavailability [164]. Lectin-induced hemagglutination is an additional concern [165]. Possible solutions to these problems include the use of non-oral, non-intravenous routes of administration and the rational design of small-molecule drugs that mimic the carbohydrate recognition domains of lectins [164].

Chitin

Because *H. illucens* larvae are capable of feeding, not just on carrion but a wide range of other decomposing organic matter, it has been suggested this species could be used in the bioconversion of food and agricultural waste to chitin (Fig. 3) [169]. Chitin is a major component of the fly larvae's exoskeleton and can be converted into chitosan, a similarly bioactive but more chemically versatile derivative, by alkaline deacetylation [170].

Chitin and chitosan are already used in wound dressings [170], and chitosan is used in farming to protect crops from infection [171]. Additional applications proposed for chitin and chitosan include drug

delivery systems (e.g. capsules) [172], burn dressings, absorbable sutures [170], medical implants (e.g. tissue engineering scaffolds) [172], antimicrobial fabrics [173], food packaging [174] and food sanitizers [175]. Chitin and chitosan are well-suited to these applications because, in addition to being antibacterial [176], they are antifungal [177], hemostatic [178], promote wound healing, have good biocompatibility, are biodegradable [170], and can be formulated into absorbent [172], oxygen-permeable [170], flexible [172], strong [179] and/or highly durable [172] materials according to need.

Currently, chitin and chitosan production from *H. illucens* larvae is not commercially feasible [169], but this may change as bioconversion is optimized through targeted breeding programs [180] and new extraction and processing methods are explored and developed [173,181,182].

Lauric acid

In addition to chitin and chitosan production, *H. illucens* could be a useful new source of lauric acid [183], a medium-chain fatty acid with antibacterial activity [184]. Lauric acid is found in high concentrations in *H. illucens* larvae, representing 44-61% of their total fatty acid profile [185]. Lauric acid is already used in soaps [186] and has been proposed as a possible anti-acne treatment and alternative to antibiotics in animal feed [183,187]. This is based, in part, on its activity against *Cutibacterium acnes* [184] and gastrointestinal pathogens [188,189] but also its excellent safety profile [183,184] and complementary activities such as antivirulence activity [183,190], AMP and immunoglobulin upregulation [191,192], anti-inflammatory activity [188,192] and animal growth promotion [192]. Obstacles hampering the development of lauric acid for the above applications are its low water solubility [184] and susceptibility to gastro-intestinal lipases [188]. Processing costs are problematic too [183]. Solutions being investigated include solubilization using liposomes [184], protection from lipases by encapsulation [191,193], and the development of novel enzyme-based processing methods [194].

Microbiota bacteria and yeasts

Several mutualistic microbiota bacteria and yeasts have been detected in carrion users including *Bacillus subtilis* (in black rats [195]), *Hylemonella gracilis*, *Lactobacillus sakei* and *Yarrowia lipolytica* (in black vultures and turkey vultures [63]), *Enterococcus faecium* and other lactic acid bacteria (in Eurasian griffons [20]), *Morganella*, *Myroides* and *Yarrowia* (in *N. vespilloides* [106,196]), *Myroides odoratimimus* (in *Sarcophaga* sp. [101]), and *Serratia myotis* (in emerald rockcods [197]). The antibacterial activity of these microbes has been attributed to AMPs (e.g. enterocins [20]), indole derivatives (e.g. violacein [63]), fatty acids (e.g. stearic acid [106]), siderophores (e.g. serranicin [197]) and surfactants (e.g. surfactin [63]), with some microbes encoding multiple active compounds [20,106].

Necrophage-sourced mutualistic microbes have been proposed for development as probiotics or ‘direct-fed microbial products’ in animal nutrition [20,197], these representing an attractive alternative to in-feed antibiotics in livestock, poultry, shrimp and fish farming [198-200]. In addition to preventing infection, prospective probiotics should be nonpathogenic (or extremely rarely pathogenic) in animals and humans [198,201], and incapable of transmitting antibiotic resistance genes [198,200]. Other important attributes include the ability to grow rapidly on inexpensive media [201], maintain viability during storage [202], survive gastric transit, attach to enterocytes or mucus [199,200] and, in the case of probiotics intended for marine aquaculture, grow at high salt concentrations [202]. If a probiotic candidate confers, not just disease protection, but positively affects weight gain or another animal performance measure, this will strengthen the economic argument for its development [203,204].

Current challenges facing animal probiotic developers are the elucidation of microbe mechanism(s) of action and assessment of microbe safety [203,205]. Information on the safety of necrophage-sourced mutualistic microbes is particularly limited because, with the exception of *B. subtilis* and *E. faecium* [201], none of the isolated species have been used previously as animal probiotics. Inconsistent results in clinical trials [203] and differences in regulation between countries [201] are other challenges. The above problems are likely to improve as technological advances allow microbiota

ecology to be monitored more accurately [206,207], risk assessment guidance is developed and refined [208], and knowledge of the variables affecting probiotic efficacy grows [198,201].

Disease-resistance genes

In addition to the traits above, the genes encoding bacterial disease resistance in carrion users could be useful. Transgenic research has already been performed with *sarcotoxin IA*, a *Sarcophaga peregrina* gene encoding an AMP. This gene, when introduced into food and cash crops, increases their resistance to citrus canker, greening disease, bacterial soft rot and wildfire disease (caused by *Xanthomonas citri*, ‘*Candidatus Liberibacter asiaticus*’, *Erwinia carotovora* and *Pseudomonas syringae*) [209-212]. The gene also confers protection from fungal phytopathogens [212], and can be introduced into orange, tomato and tobacco plants without apparent negative effects on growth or development [209,213,214].

A current hindrance to transgenic crop development is jurisdictional variation in regulation, which complicates market access and disincentivizes investment [215]. This situation may change as more data on transgenic crop safety and environmental impact becomes available [216], and issues such as food poverty [217] and global population growth [218] receive greater attention. In addition to this general obstacle, there may be challenges specific to an introduced gene or gene product. For example, the AMP sarcotoxin IA is susceptible to proteases present in some plant intercellular fluids [211,213]. Possible solutions to this problem include linking *sarcotoxin IA* with a gene encoding a more stable protein [213] or using a high-expression promoter to increase sarcotoxin IA synthesis [211,212].

Concluding remarks

Many antibacterial drugs and products in current use were developed from nature, including some, such as streptomycin, which were discovered via ecology-inspired bioprospecting. Past bioprospecting projects have focused largely on soil- and marine-dwelling microbes and plants, but interest is growing in carrion

ecology and carrion users. In this review, we have catalogued over 660 such species, including 625 necrophages (≥ 46 obligately necrophagous) and 44 necrophiles (Suppl Tables 1 and 4). Information collected on the types of carrion consumed and the bacterial species detected in, on and around carrion shows necrophages and necrophiles are exposed to a diverse range of pathogens. The selection pressure to evolve, acquire and retain antibacterial defenses is likely to be stronger in these animals, therefore, than other trophic groups. Necrophage and necrophile defenses studied so far include toxin-resistant anatomies, risk reduction behaviors and enhancements in innate immunity, social immunity, adaptive immunity and detoxification systems. In some cases, the genes, molecules and microbes responsible for these defenses have been identified, and we have described their possible applications in drug treatments, medical devices and food production.

The present paper has a number of strengths and limitations. It is, to our knowledge, the first review to look at the bacterial pathogens to which carrion users are exposed, the first review of antibacterial defenses in invertebrate necrophages and necrophiles (for earlier work on vertebrates, see [219]), and the first review of biotechnological applications for necrophage- and necrophile-derived genes, molecules and microbes. To provide readers with as full a picture as possible, we consulted over 500 sources, including original articles, review articles and conference proceedings identified from PubMed, ScienceDirect, Google Scholar and hand searches. Set against these strengths, we acknowledge the following limitations. Firstly, because of the extremely large number of articles documenting necrophagy and necrophily, it has not been possible to comprehensively catalogue all of the animal species in these trophic groups. It has not even been possible to catalogue all of the probable obligate necrophages as some invertebrate genera, for example *Nicrophorus*, contain over 60 species [220]. Also, new species of marine necrophage, for example hagfish, have been discovered as recently as 2021 [221] and their diets are not yet fully characterized. Secondly, we did not assess the strength of evidence that the proposed antibacterial defenses confer *in situ* protection from infection or intoxication. Such assessments, whilst important, can be very contentious. In the case of streptomycin and other soil-derived antibiotics,

scientific consensus regarding their ecological role remains elusive many decades after their successful clinical development [222].

Regarding future research, we have several suggestions. Given the large number of known necrophages and necrophiles, it would be useful to develop evidence-based criteria for prioritizing species for antibacterial studies [e.g. reliance on carrion as a food source (Suppl Tables 1 and 4); engaging in risky feeding behaviors (Suppl Table 3)]. Also, given the importance of necrophagous and necrophilous invertebrates in forensic studies, and the necessity for regional research within this discipline [69], there should be opportunities for ecologists and biotechnologists to pool resources with forensic scientists. Forensic science has already yielded an abundance of basic information on which invertebrates are necrophagous or necrophilous, and greater interdisciplinary cooperation would allow complementary information to be generated on their antibacterial defenses and biotechnological potential. For researchers who successfully isolate AMPs or other antibacterial molecules, we would encourage fully quantitative testing using internationally recognized technical standards to accurately determine MICs and selectivity index values [12]. Also, for researchers developing mutualistic microbiota organisms as animal probiotics, the European Food Safety Authority and US Food and Drug Administration websites [223,224] and associated publications [208,225] are useful sources of technical information. Lastly, suitable precautions should be taken during all carrion studies to reduce the risk of zoonosis and harm to threatened wildlife. Several necrophages, such as *Gyps indicus* (Indian vulture) and *Nicrophorus americanus* (American burying beetle), are already critically endangered [226].

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The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

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Table 1 Examples of (a) antimicrobial peptides and (b) small-molecule antibacterials isolated from necrophages, necrophiles and their microbiotas, together with information on their minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) and how these MICs were determined.

Compound	Source	MIC assay	Cell density (CFU mL ⁻¹)	MIC (µg mL ⁻¹)		Reference(s)
				Gram-positive	Gram-negative	
(a) AMPs						
DLP2	<i>Hermetia illucens</i>	BMID	5 × 10 ⁴	0.03 to 4.0	NA	[121]*
C-15867	<i>Hermetia illucens</i>	NS	5 × 10 ⁵	0.16 to 0.28	0.16	[133]
Sapecin	<i>Sarcophaga peregrina</i>	AD	NS	1.2 to 39.0	20.0 to >78.0	[134]
Peptide 9	<i>Sarcophaga peregrina</i>	AD	NS	1.6 to 24.9	1.5 to 24.9	[135]
Sarconesin	<i>Sarconesia magellanica</i> †	BMID	5 × 10 ⁴	1.8 to 6.9	3.5 to 6.9	[122,136]*
Lucifensin	<i>Lucilia sericata</i>	BMID	5 × 10 ⁵	2.0 to >100	NA	[137]
Stomoxyn	<i>Lucilia sericata</i>	BMID	5 × 10 ⁵	NA	2.0 to >100	[22]*
Cecropin 4	<i>Musca domestica</i>	BMID	5 × 10 ⁵	4.3 to >100	2.2 to 8.7	[138]
Peptide 0593	<i>Periplaneta americana</i>	BMID	2 × 10 ⁴	16.0	4.0	[139]*
Sarcotoxin IA	<i>Sarcophaga peregrina</i>	ABA	1 × 10 ⁵	NT	4.2	[140,141]
(b) Small-molecule antibacterials‡						
Solenopsin B	<i>Solenopsis invicta</i>	BMID	5 × 10 ⁵	0.5 to ≥32.0	>5.0	[142,143]*
Serrawettin W2	<i>Serratia marcescens</i> (from <i>Nicrophorus vespilloides</i>)	BMID	5 × 10 ⁵	4.0	NA	[144]
Nicrophorus-amide A	<i>Microbacterium</i> sp. (from <i>Nicrophorus concolor</i>)	BMID	5 × 10 ⁵	8.0 to 16.0	16.0 to >100	[145]

Notes: MIC, minimum inhibitory concentration; ABA, Alamar Blue assay; AD, agar dilution assay; BMID, broth microdilution assay; NS, not stated; NA, not active (MIC >100µg mL⁻¹); NT, not tested; *, authors identified more than one active compound; †, *Sarconesiopsis magellanica* is a synonym of *Sarconesia magellanica*; ‡, solenopsin B is an alkaloid, serrawettin W2 is a cyclic pentadepsipeptide, and nicrophorusamide A is a chlorinated cyclic hexapeptide

Figure 1 Examples of different carrion users: (a) *Nicrophorus vespillo* (common burying beetle), an obligate necrophage feeding on mole carrion, (b) *Corvus corone* (carrion crow), a facultative necrophage feeding on roadkilled pigeon and (c) *Nasonia vitripennis*, a necrophile parasitizing a *Calliphora vomitoria* (blue bottle fly) pupa. Photograph (a) by RhinoMind and photograph (b) by Marie-Lan Taÿ Pamart (both used under Creative Commons CC BY-SA 4.0 license). Photograph (c) by Koppik et al. [28] (used under Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 license).

Figure 2 Lectins could be useful as (a) antivirulence drugs because they bind to carbohydrate-containing molecules such as lipoteichoic acid, preventing bacterial cells from attaching to host tissue. Lectins could also be useful in (b) drug delivery systems targeting bacterial infection if incorporated into the membranes of antibiotic-loaded liposomes or fused with AMPs. Image (a) adapted from Fonseca et al. [165] by permission of Elsevier, and image (b) adapted from Carneiro et al. [164] by permission of Wiley.

Figure 3 *Hermetia illucens* could be useful in chitin production: (a) *H. illucens* larvae feeding on agricultural waste, (b) exuviae obtained from waste-fed larvae, (c) oven-dried and ground exuviae and (d) a scanning electron micrograph of chitin obtained from exuviae powder after demineralization and fat and protein removal (bar = 50 μm). Photograph (a) by Fowles and Nansen [180] (used under Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 license) and photographs (b), (c) and (d) by Bhavsar et al. [173] (used under Creative Commons CC BY-NC-ND 4.0 license).

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Supplementary Table 1 Examples of vertebrate necrophages, information on whether they are obligately or facultatively necrophagous, and other dietary details such as types of carrion they feed upon.

Supplementary Table 2 Examples of bacteria causing fatal infections and toxico-infections of wildlife, livestock and other animals, and which are transmissible by contact with or ingestion of contaminated carcasses.

Supplementary Table 3 Necrophages and necrophiles engaging in behaviors that might increase their risk or their offspring's risk of infection.

Supplementary Table 4 Examples of invertebrate necrophages and necrophiles, information on whether this feeding behavior is obligate or facultative (where available), and other dietary details such as type of carrion they feed upon or visit in search of eggs, larvae or pupae.

Supplementary Table 5 Examples of antimicrobial peptides (AMPs; ≤ 50 amino acid- or ≤ 5.5 kDa-sized molecules) detected in necrophages and necrophiles.

Supplementary Table 6 Examples of antibacterial proteins (> 50 amino acid- or > 5.5 kDa-sized molecules) detected in necrophages and necrophiles.